

BIODEGRADABILITY OF A SILKWORM SILK FIBER REINFORCED POLY(LACTIC ACID) BIOCOMPOSITE

H. Y. Cheung* and K. T. Lau

Department of Mechanical Engineering, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University,
Hung Hom, Hong Kong

karen.chy@gmail.com*, mmkklau@polyu.edu.hk

SUMMARY

Previous researches investigated the impact of silk fibers upon polymeric materials and gave attention to the development of biodegradable biocomposites [1-4]. The purpose of this study is to advance the understanding of the mechanical properties of different types of silk fibers and the biodegradability of a silk fiber reinforced PLA biocomposite.

Keywords: Silkworm silk fiber, biocomposite, biodegradation, mechanical properties, surface analysis

INTRODUCTION

Silkworm silk fiber (hereafter 'silk fiber') is obtained from cocoon produced by domesticated mulberry silkworm (*Bombyx mori*), which is usually white toned and more reproducible, and wild silkworms (*Tussah*) live naturally in tropical or semi-tropical forests and eat all kinds of leaves from different trees which are rich in tannin, their fiber is beige to brownish toned. *Tussah* silk fiber is produced by caterpillars (silkworms) and cannot be artificially cultivated [5-6]. Silk fiber is constructed with two different protein-based layers – fibroin filaments in an inner layer and a sericin coating in an outer layer which acts like an envelope to bind the fibroins together. Long and continuous fiber can only be spun when the sericin coating is degummed from the cocoon structure, which is generally performed by soaking the silk fiber in hot or boiling water [7]. Silk fiber is a natural protein fiber which is biodegradable and highly crystalline with a well-aligned structure.

Biocompatibility and biodegradability play important roles in the bioengineering process of the regeneration of neo-tissues, which can subsequently affect cells vitality, cell growth and even host response. It is believed that the ideal *in vivo* degradation rate may be similar or slightly less than the rate of tissue formation which can maintain tissue integrity of implantation site and continually transferring the load bearing burden to the regenerating biological functional tissues are highly desired. This gradual load transfer at a predictable and controllable rate is especially important to mechanical sensitive tissue. Poly(lactic acid) (PLA), poly(glycolic acid) (PGA) and their copolymers have been the most widely used to date and are found to be biocompatible while at the same time being able to provide suitable mechanical strength for the implant applications. During biodegradation, these materials degrade into smaller

fragments as well as monomers, such as lactic acid, that can be eliminated by normal metabolic processes of the body. However, when PLA is fabricated as porous scaffold, its mechanical properties will drop dramatically and may not provide sufficient strength for load-bearing applications. To address this problem, silk fiber may be a good alternative as reinforcement to enhance the strength of PLA. The aim of the present work is to characterize a novel type of biocomposites and investigate the mechanical properties of single and twisted silk fibers. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to observe the morphology of two different types of silk fibers, and measure their apparent diameters. Furthermore, biodegradation test followed by physical and mechanical analysis were performed in order to study the biodegradability of silk/PLA biocomposite for biomedical and bioengineering applications.

PRELIMINARY STUDIES

Analysis of silk fibers

'As-received' raw silk fibers with two different silkworm raising processes, cocoon producing and spinning conditions were tested in this study: (i) *Bombyx mori*; (ii) twisted *Bombyx mori* (for comparison of tensile properties with the single fiber); and (iii) Tussah silk fibers. The determination of stress-strain relationship requires the value of cross-sectional area of tested specimens. The mean or apparent fiber diameter was estimated from SEM images taken at five different regions of each fiber. Results obtained from earlier studies [8-10] generally agreed with the area of a non-cylindrical like fiber, spider silk. Therefore, the area of silkworm silk fiber can be accurately calculated by assuming the fiber cross-section is circular, and by rotating the sample platform around its axis inside the microscope. Two different orientations (0° and 90°) were used to estimate the apparent diameter of silk fiber as shown in Figure 1. A tensile test was then performed to compare the mechanical properties of the cocoon spun silk fibers. Samples were randomly selected in a bundle of fibers and 10 contiguous experimental samples were used in each of the selected fiber (i.e. 30 testing samples in total). This sampling method can avoid high intrinsic scatter of the test data for the similarity of the tensile properties of consecutive samples, which is commonly used for spider and silkworm silk fibers. Silk fiber was cut gently into short fiber fractions in the length of 70 mm to make sure that the fiber was not stressed plastically during the process. Every chopped fiber was mounted and taped across a hole which is 30 mm long of a rectangular cardboard which was fixed in an Instron mechanical testing machine (25 N) [11]. The fiber gauge length was 30 mm between the two grips of the machine. The cardboard was then cut along the dotted lines and separated into two parts to ensure tensile loading was completely transmitted to the fiber during test. All tests were conducted at a rate of 1 mm/min under ambient condition of 22°C and 45 % humidity.

Biodegradation Test

5 mm 5 wt% Tussah silk/PLA biocomposites were fabricated by extrusion and injection molding techniques as previous studies to ensure that consistent results could be obtained. The resultant biocomposite samples were in a dumbbell shape according to ASTM D638. A total of 40 samples were fabricated: 20 pure PLA samples and 20

silk/PLA biocomposites. Biodegradation test was performed in vitro by making use of Dulbecco's Phosphate Buffered Saline (PBS), two different types of dumbbell-shaped samples were immersed in two separate containers with 1xPBS solution and the containers were stored in a humidified, thermo-stable and orbital-shaking incubator at 37 °C for up to 16 weeks. During the first week of the test, pH values of 1xPBS solution in each of the containers were measured daily in order to understand the stability of the acidity of the solution. The used 1xPBS solution was replaced by fresh 1xPBS solution at the end of each week to mimic the fairly constant acidity environment in vivo. Four specific degradation testing time points were set at a 4-week interval, i.e. 4, 8, 12 and 16 weeks. At each time point, 5 pure PLA samples and 5 silk/PLA biocomposites were taken out from the containers for physical and mechanical properties characterization. The pH values of two different set of samples were checked weekly by pH meter and compared with the fresh 1xPBS solution as reference before being replaced by new 1xPBS solution. Weight loss and changes in appearance of the samples due to the release of acidic products to the solution were examined at the specific testing time point. Tensile test was then carried out to examine the mechanical properties of the samples according to the ASTM standard by using the 50 kN tensile machine and extensometer. The span length of the extensometer was 25 mm, and crosshead speed with a loading rate of 2 mm/min was used. A total of five pure PLA samples and five silk/PLA biocomposites were tested at each specific time point. After the mechanical property tests, microscopic analysis was conducted with the help of SEM on the fracture surface of the samples to examine the failure surface structure and failure behavior induced by previous tensile test. Analysis was performed at room temperature with tungsten filament, and an accelerating voltage of 20 kV was used to capture SEM images for both of the pure PLA sample and silk/PLA biocomposite. All specimens were viewed from the top of the fractured surface.

Figure 1 Two different orientations of silk fiber used to estimate its apparent diameter.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Surface analysis of silk fibers

The anisotropy of silk fibers was calculated by the axial ratio of the diameter at 0 ° (or 90 °) to the diameter at 90 ° (or 0 °) orientations, i.e. the larger diameter to the smaller diameter according to the measurement. Figures 2 and 3 show some of the selected micrographs taken at different orientations of different silk fibers. According to Dunaway et al. [9], the cross-sections of the two different silk fibers can be assumed as circular for the values of anisotropy smaller than 1.5. The apparent diameter was calculated by collecting five different data on each fiber at different orientations and

regions. The anisotropy of Tussah silk fiber is in the range of 1.18-1.42 whereas for Bombyx mori silk fiber, its anisotropy is in the range of 1.31-1.37 which is more consistent than that of the Tussah silk fiber. Yet, the cross-sectional shapes of the two different silk fibers can be assumed as circular for the values of anisotropy smaller than 1.5. After averaging the results, the apparent diameters of Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fibers are 260 μm and 85 μm respectively which can then be further used for converting the mechanical properties data. Furthermore, Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fibers have entirely different appearances for their fiber and inner fibroin filaments. As seen from Figures 2 and 3, Bombyx mori silk fiber has a larger apparent diameter, about triple to that of the Tussah silk fiber and this may be the reason for their differences in mechanical properties. On the other hand, there are more than 600 fibroin filaments included in one Bombyx mori silk fiber which has an irregularly triangular shape, and the apparent diameter is just about 10 μm . However, there are only around 10 fibroin filaments for each Tussah silk fiber which has an irregularly elongated wedge shape, with the apparent diameter of about 25 μm .

Figure 2 Measurement of Bombyx mori (on the left); and Tussah silk fibers (on the right) at 0° orientation.

Figure 3 Measurement of Bombyx mori (on the left); and Tussah silk fibers (on the right) at 90° orientation.

Mechanical Properties of silk fibers

In Figure 4(a), Bombyx mori silk fiber supports a much higher loading (about 10 N) than the Tussah silk fiber, which can withstand a maximum load of only about 2 N. Whereas for twisted Bombyx mori silk fiber, with a cross sectional area of double to

that of the single one, it is doubtless that it can bear an even higher loading. It takes about 19 N, only almost a double, to that of the single Bombyx mori silk fiber which is mainly due to the majority part of loading on tension and a small portion of loading overcomes the friction among the twisted fibers. In addition, for the extensibility, Tussah silk fiber has a greater elongation of about 89 % than the Bombyx mori silk fiber, and the twisted Bombyx mori silk fiber exhibits a slightly larger elongation than the single one with about 17 % increment. Shao and Vollrath [6] have pointed out that under slow spinning speed, Bombyx mori silk fiber could obtain a large breaking elongation but mechanically, it became weaker; whereas with faster spinning speed, it could have a breaking energy approached to Nephila silk, but the silk became more brittle due to the loss of extensibility. This shows that distinct feeding habits, cocoon spinning environment and speed etc. on Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fiber have a great effect upon their overall mechanical properties. Besides, Bombyx mori silk fiber has a larger apparent diameter but with a smaller cross-sectional area of each fibroin filament (i.e. less necking of each fibroin filament during tensile loading can be obtained) than Tussah silk fiber, so it may be incontestably concluded that Bombyx mori silk fiber can bear a higher loading but has a relatively lower extensibility than Tussah silk fiber.

Based on experimental results obtained as shown in Table 1 and Figure 4(b), it was found that the specific Tussah silk fibers exhibit a better ultimate tensile strength and extensibility whereas the stiffness values of both of the species are almost the same. Apart from this, the SEM micrographs show the apparent diameter of the Bombyx mori silk fiber is triple to the Tussah silk fiber, and the twisted Bombyx mori silk fiber is assumed to be doubled of the single fiber. Therefore, although single and twisted Bombyx mori silk fiber can bear a higher tensile loading, when analyzing the data into stress-strain curves, Tussah silk fiber indicates the highest ultimate tensile strength. The apparent diameter of Bombyx mori silk fibroin filament is much smaller than that of the Tussah silk fibroin filament which can be accounted for less extensibility, so, single and twisted Bombyx mori silk fibers show only about 20 % elongation at break. Silk fiber is made up of both crystalline and non-crystalline regions in which the interconnected and well-aligned region would account for the stiffness of the fiber, whereas the disordered region would account for the ability of elongation at break (failure). The behavior of silk fiber under tensile loading is generally accounted for the changes on molecular level also [12]. When a tensile load is applied, initial deformation occurs primarily in amorphous region. When the load is applied continuously, inter-chain bonds are broken, more and more randomly arranged or disordered chains are further extended, and the load will then begin to be taken up by the crystalline region. Due to the high proportion of crystalline structure in domesticated Bombyx mori silk fiber, the stress-strain curve is approximately parabolic and slightly convex to load axis up to break. A relatively high proportion of amorphous structure in wild Tussah silk fiber can be account for its pronounced yield plateau and a distinct concave curve up to break.

Table 1 Mechanical properties of Bombyx mori, twisted Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fibers.

Silk fiber samples	UTS (MPa)	Strain at break (%)	E (GPa)
Bombyx mori	208.45	19.55	6.10

	(10N)		
Twisted Bombyx mori	165.27	20.57	3.82
	(19N)		
Tussah	248.77	33.48	5.79
	(2 N)		

Figure 4(a) Force-displacement and (b) stress-strain curves of Bombyx mori, twisted Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fibers.

Biodegradation Test

After the 16-week biodegradation test, the pH value of the 1xPBS solution remained almost same in the range of pH 7.37 and 7.41 for both pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites. Moreover, the weight of two different types of samples remain unchanged at 1.3 g for the first 12 weeks and dropped slightly to 1.24 g for pure PLA samples and 1.26 g for the silk/PLA biocomposites at the last time point (16 weeks) of the biodegradation test. Consequently, the degradation does not affect the pH value significantly and mass change with time was slow in general. On the other hand, the appearances of pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites remained unchanged in the first 4 weeks of the test, and they started to change from transparent to translucent and from yellow to pale yellow in color respectively afterward. Curves of ultimate tensile strength and modulus of elasticity against biodegradation time are as shown in Figures 5(a)-(b). Dotted line in the figures represents the mechanical property results of the silk/PLA biocomposites. For the ultimate tensile strength, the pure PLA samples

degraded constantly against time whereas the silk/PLA biocomposites degraded in a faster rate in the first 2 weeks, followed by a constant rate of biodegradation. On the other hand, regarding the modulus of elasticity of the two different types of samples, it can be observed from Figure 5(b) that silk fiber enhanced the stiffness of PLA in the beginning, and silk/PLA biocomposites degraded constantly with a relatively faster biodegradation rate than that of the pure PLA samples during the biodegradation test. Some proteinous materials such as silk fibroin, elastin and amino acids etc. were found to stimulate the production of enzymes from PLA-degrading micro-organisms [13-14]. Additionally, silk fiber is hydrophilic whereas PLA is hydrophobic polymer which can only absorb about 1 % water content; therefore, silk fiber will be the major factor affecting the water absorption ability of the composite. Increment on silk fiber content leads to a faster water absorption rate of the material due to its strong hydrophilic property, while for PLA, moisture susceptibility is the primary driving force towards biodegradation. Thereby, the area exposed to hydrolysis increased with the reinforcement of silk fiber, resulting in a higher biodegradation rate of the biocomposite. It can be claimed that the biodegradation rate of PLA could be improved and controlled by reinforcements of silk fiber which induces porous structure to pure PLA materials. By controlling the biodegradation rate of implant materials, the regeneration rate of neo-tissues at implantation site can be matched; load-bearing functions can be transferred desirably from the implants to the neo-tissues.

Figure 5 Curves of (a) ultimate tensile strength and (b) modulus of elasticity against biodegradation time of pure PLA and silk/PLA biocomposite samples (dotted line).

After tensile test, the morphology of the fracture surface of pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites was then sent for SEM investigations. Micrographs of two different types of samples after the biodegradation test at specific time points were as shown in Figures 6(a)-(e). It can be observed that the surface morphology of the pure PLA samples became smoother from 4 weeks up to 12 weeks, and it is obvious that from the mechanical property test, the ductility of the samples is increasing from the beginning of the test up to 12 weeks. Samples became relatively brittle at 16th week of the test. On the other hand, the silk/PLA biocomposites became more rubbery on the surface up to 8 weeks of the biodegradation test, which is mainly due to the serious water absorption problem. Besides, larger portion of PLA in the silk/PLA biocomposite was degraded at 12 and 16 weeks of the test as the interfacial bonding between silk fiber and PLA became weaker, and more water was absorbed by the fiber than before.

Figure 6 SEM images of pure PLA (left) and silk/PLA biocomposite samples (right) (a) before; (b) after 4 weeks; (c) after 8 weeks; (d) after 12 weeks; and (e) after 16 weeks of biodegradation test.

CONCLUSIONS

Since silk fiber has a great variability in appearance and dimension for different species of silkworms, the appearances and apparent diameters of the Bombyx mori and Tussah silk fibers were examined for converting experimental data into stress-strain analysis. The specific Tussah silk fiber exhibits a better ultimate tensile strength and extensibility whereas the stiffness values of both of the species are almost identical. This may be due to the distinction of silkworm raising processes, cocoon producing and spinning conditions of the fiber. Although different species of silkworms produce different types of silk fiber with completely diverse set of properties, they can be applied to various applications according to their distinct properties or even tailor-made to suit some specifications. Pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites were examined under the in vitro biodegradation test for 16 weeks, the acidity of degradation product from both pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites are mild and do not affect the in vivo environment. The appearance of pure PLA samples and silk/PLA biocomposites started to change in color after the 4th week of the test and mass change with time for both set of samples was slow in general. For the mechanical property test of the biodegraded samples, stiffness and ductility of PLA were enhanced with the reinforcement of silk fiber. Biodegradation rate of the PLA was seen to be improved and controlled with the reinforcements of silk fiber which induces porous structure to the matrix for faster rate of water intake due to its strong hydrophilic ability. It is concluded that silk fiber can be a potential candidate as reinforcement for biocomposite as the biodegradation rate of implants can be controlled so as to match with the regeneration duration of neo-tissues at implantation site to fulfill its desired function.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was supported by The Hong Kong Polytechnic University Grant and Research Grant Council (PolyU 5205/06E and 5198/07E).

REFERENCES

1. Priya S.P., Ramakrishna H.V. and Rai S.K.. Tensile, flexural, and chemical resistance properties of waste silk fabric-reinforced epoxy laminates. *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*. Vol 24, pp 643-648, 2005.
2. Lee S.M., Cho D.H., Park W.H., Lee S.G., Han S.O. and Drzal L.T.. Novel silk/poly(butylenes succinate) biocomposites: the effect of short fiber content on their mechanical and thermal properties. *Composites Science and Technology*. Vol 65, pp 647-657, 2005.
3. Han S.O., Lee S.M., Park W.H. and Cho H.. Mechanical and thermal properties of waste silk fiber-reinforced poly(butylenes succinate) biocomposites. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*. Vol 100, pp 4972-4980, 2006.
4. Lee K.G., Kweon H.Y., Yeo J.H., Woo S.O., Lee J.H. and Park Y.H.. Structural and physical properties of silk fibroin/alginate blend sponges. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*. Vol 93, pp 2174-2179, 2004.
5. Zhao H.P., Feng X.Q., Yu S.W., Cui W.Z. and Zou F.Z.. Mechanical properties of silkworm cocoons. *Polymer* 2005; 46: 9192-9201.
6. Shao Z. and Vollrath F.. Surprising strength of silkworm silk. *Nature* 2002; 418: 741.
7. Lee S.M., Cho D. Park W.H., Lee S.G., Han S.O. and Drzal L.T.. Novel silk/poly (butylenes succinate) biocomposites: the effect of short fiber content on their mechanical and thermal properties. *Composites Science and Technology* 2005; 65: 647-657.
8. Rigueiro J.P., Elices M., Llorca J. and Viney C.. Tensile properties of *Argiope trifasciata* drag line silk obtained from spider's web. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 2001; 82: 2245-2251.
9. Dunaway D.L., Thiel B.L., Srinivasan S.G. and Viney C.. Characterizing the cross-sectional geometry of thin, non-cylindrical, twisted fibers (spider silk). *Journal of Materials Science* 1995; 30: 4161-4170.
10. Rigueiro J.P., Viney C., Llorca J. and Elices M.. Mechanical properties of single-brin silkworm silk. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 2000; 75: 1270-1277.
11. Rigueiro J.P., Viney C., Llorca J. and Elices M.. Silkworm silk as an engineering material. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 1998; 70: 2439-2447.
12. Robson R.M.. Silk. Composition, structure and properties. In: Lewin M. and Pearce E.M., editors. *Handbook of fiber chemistry*, 2nd ed.. New York: Marcel Dekker, Inc.; 1998.
13. Agrawal C.M., McKinney J.S., Lanctot D. and Athanasiou K.A.. Effects of fluid flow on the in vitro degradation kinetics of biodegradable scaffolds for tissue engineering. *Biomaterials* 2000; 21: 2443-2452.
14. Tokiwa Y. and Calabia B.P.. Biodegradability and biodegradation of poly(lactide). *Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology* 2006; 72: 244-251.